

Magnetic nanoparticles and their applications

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Abstract : The aim of this article is to provide updated, concise yet accurate information about nanotechnology and magnetic nanoparticles in the fields of high societal impact such as environment and biomedicines based on scientific literatures and authoritative reports. The article also includes some visions of potential of applications of nanotechnology, whilst keeping the discussion at the realistic level. This article has been written with the purpose of supporting and enhancing the knowledge of college students, non-governmental organizations, trade unions and industrial workers, as well as other working groups in learning about the nanotechnology and magnetic nanoparticles and its potential in these diverse areas of applications. The authors' intention is to provide those groups forming a balanced view of nanotechnology and magnetic nanoparticles, so to promote a constructive dialogue about this emerging technology. Other aspects of this discussion, such as potential environmental risks of nanoparticles, health and safety aspects, and challenges related to nanotechnology has been also covered in this article.

1. Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology is the emerging field in science and technology and is poised to bring in revolutionary changes across all spheres of life. Nanotechnology can be applied across a wide variety of fields, right from medicine, textile and education to defense and manufacturing. Several focus groups across the country are working on bringing innovations in their respective fields of specialization. A student can opt for applied and basic research in this field across all these fields. So here it becomes necessary to tell our readers that what is the nanotechnology? First, we will classify the

concept “nano”. The term “nano” is derived from the Greek word for “dwarf”, “nanos”. This etymology, and its placement on the metric scale ($1 \text{ nm} = 10^{-9} \text{ m}$), make it clear that tiny dimensions not visible to the naked eye, beyond the normal limits of our observation, are involved¹.

2. Careers in nanotechnology in India

The nanotechnology impact on India is predicted to be larger than the information technology and internet boom. The epicenter of this boom will be in places like Bangalore and Chennai which are the hub of manufacturing, information technology and medicine. The Indian government has already started nanoscience and nanotechnology initiatives and various funding agencies like the Department of Science and Technology, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Indian Council of Medical Research, Indian Council of Agriculture Research, and Defense Research & Development Organization. Department of Science and Technology constitutes a Nano Mission Council which has been operating across many educational institutions, majority of which are in the South. Some of the Southern institutions that have dedicated nanotechnology research centers funded by the council are Indian Institute of Sciences in Bangalore, Sastra University in Tanjavur, Karunya University in Coimbatore, Osmania University in Hyderabad, Anna University in Chennai and Vellore Institute of Technology in Vellore. Recently, the Institute of Nanoscience and Technology has been opened at Mohali in Punjab for the research and development in North India. The council provides an opportunity to research and helps in addressing issues across a wide spectrum of topics like Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS), nanostructure synthesis and characterizations, DNA chips, nanoelectronics and nanomaterials. The council provides adequate funding for research in basic and applied areas of nanotechnology and also for training manpower in nanotechnology. Currently it is used in healthcare to treat diabetes, skin problems and cancer. It is also being used in water purification. A student should come with an open mind to pursue this course. The application of fundamentals is very necessary. He should be well-versed with subjects such as Physics, Chemistry, and Biology. It allows a student to explore and innovate. So an objective and rational approach towards research and innovation is very important in this field.

Recently, various types of nanomaterials such as magnetic nanoparticles,

titanium dioxide, carbon nanotubes, graphene-based adsorbents, zinc oxides, and layered double hydroxides have been widely explored for their efficient application in the biological field and for the treatment and restoration of water/wastewater. In this article, we will briefly discuss the synthesis and application of magnetic nanoparticles for the biological applications and as adsorbents for the treatment and remediation of pollutants from water/wastewater.

3. Magnetic nanoparticles

During the last 5 years, magnetic nanoparticles, due to their magnetic properties, high chemical stability, low toxicity and ease in synthesis and excellent recycling capability, have aroused extensive attention and have been extensively studied to remove toxic metal ions and organic pollutants from water, and these materials show higher removal capacities than the bulk material. Their nanoscale-sized overall structure provides the necessary mechanical robustness against wear and tear; and provides the high surface area as well as the high removal capacity for heavy metal ions and dyes. Magnetic nanoparticles have a wide range of application including magnetic fluids, catalysis, biomedicine, drug delivery, magnetic resonance imaging, data storage, and environmental remediation²⁻⁷.

Several appropriate methods have been developed for the synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles of a variety of different compositions. In majority of the envisaged applications, the particles perform best when the size of the nanoparticles is below a critical value, which is dependent on the source material but is normally around 10–20 nm⁴. The design and synthesis of nanoparticle-based adsorbents has generated great interest in a variety of scientific communities ranging from chemical, biological and environmental science to engineering. Magnetic nanoparticle-based adsorbents can be used in the separation and purification of heavy metals and toxic dyes from aqueous solution with high precision and accuracy⁶⁻¹¹.

However, the bare magnetic nanoparticles are very prone to the atmospheric conditions as it easily get oxidized the open air and water. Hence, scientist have coated or functionalized the magnetic nanoparticles to enhance the functional groups and to stabilize the synthesized magnetic nanoparticles in the extreme environmental conditions. Functionalized mag-

netic nanoparticles are very promising for applications in catalysis, reduction and oxidation of pollutants; and for the separation of heavy metals and hazardous dyes. Extraction of heavy metal and dyes from their liquid phase with such small and magnetically separable particles may be useful as they combine the advantages of high dispersion, high reactivity, high stability under acidic conditions, and through the easy recycling of used adsorbents in separation. Synthesis and application of magnetic nanoparticles for the separation and purification of hazardous pollutants from the aqueous solutions have been discussed in this section.

Co-precipitation is a very simple and convenient way to synthesize iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles (either Fe_3O_4 or $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) from aqueous $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ salt solutions by the addition of a base under inert atmosphere at room temperature or at elevated temperature as per the desired phase of the magnetic nanoparticles. The chemical reaction of Fe_3O_4 formation can be written as¹²

According to the thermodynamics of this reaction, complete precipitation of Fe_3O_4 should be expected at pH between 8 and 12, with a stoichiometric ratio of 2 : 1 ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$) in the nitrogen atmosphere. The size, shape, and composition of the magnetic nanoparticles very much depends on the type of salts used (e.g. chlorides, sulfates, nitrates), the $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio, the reaction temperature, the pH value and ionic strength of the media. Once the synthetic conditions are fixed, the quality of the magnetic nanoparticles is fully reproducible. However, magnetite nanoparticles are not very stable under ambient conditions, and are easily get oxidized to maghemite or easily precipitate in an acidic medium.

Since oxidation of magnetite is the lesser problem than it is a ferrimagnet. Therefore, magnetite particles can be subjected to deliberate oxidation to convert them into maghemite. This transformation is achieved by dispersing them in acidic medium, then addition of iron(III) nitrate. The maghemite particles obtained are then chemically stable in alkaline and acidic medium⁴. The main advantage of the co-precipitation process is that

a bulk amount of magnetic nanoparticles can be easily synthesized in a short time with low cost precursors. However, the control of particle size distribution is limited, because only kinetic factors are controlling the growth of the crystal¹². In the syntheses of magnetic nanoparticles by co-precipitation route, mainly two stages are involved, a short burst of nucleation occurs when the concentration of the species reaches critical supersaturation, and then, there is a slow growth of the nuclei by diffusion of the solutes to the surface of the crystal. To fabricate monodisperse iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles, these two key stages should be separated; i.e. nucleation should be avoided during the period of enlargement.

4. Applications of magnetic nanoparticles

4.1. Biomedicines and clinical uses

Magnetic nanoparticles have found notable and successful applications in biology and biomedicine, such as pathogen detection, proteins separation, drug delivery, and hyperthermia. The most prominent biomedical application of magnetic nanoparticles is that they act magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents, which already received some clinical acceptance. In this section we focus on the applications of magnetic nanoparticles inside the cells, such as cell tracking by MR imaging, intracellular manipulation of biomolecules by a magnetic force, and encapsulation of potential anticancer agents. For biomedical uses, the application of particles that present superparamagnetic behavior at room temperature is preferred¹³. Furthermore, applications in therapy and biology and medical diagnosis require the magnetic particles to be stable in water at pH 7 and in a physiological environment. The colloidal stability of this fluid will depend on the charge and surface chemistry, which give rise to both steric and coulombic repulsions and also depend on the dimensions of the particles, which should be sufficiently small so that precipitation due to gravitation forces can be avoided. Additional restrictions to the possible particles could be used for biomedical applications (i.e. *in vivo* or *in vitro* applications). For *in vivo* applications, the magnetic nanoparticles must be encapsulated with a biocompatible polymer during or after the preparation process to prevent changes from the original structure, the formation of large aggregates, and biodegradation when exposed to the biological system. The nanoparticle

coated with polymer will also allow binding of drugs by entrapment on the particles, adsorption, or covalent attachment.

4.2. MRI and cell tracking

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a diagnostic technique used primarily in medical settings to produce high quality anatomical images of the human body. In clinical practice, as a noninvasive modality that uses strong magnetic fields and non-ionizing radiation in the radio frequency range, MRI can distinguish pathologic tissue (e.g. tumors) from normal tissue, mostly by anatomical differences. The recent development of molecular and cellular imaging, which aims for visualizing the disease-specific biomarkers at the molecular and cellular levels, has led to prevalent recognition of the magnetic nanoparticles as MRI contrast agents¹⁴. Mainly based on the cellular uptake of magnetic nanoparticles, cellular MRI (CMRI) can track the temporal and spatial migration of cells labeled with magnetic resonance contrast agents within organs and tissues.

4.3. Tissue engineering

Tissue engineering is an interdisciplinary area of nanomedicine in which biomaterial and medical science understands of pathological tissue and the principles used to achieve this understanding are applied to the improving or sustaining of tissue function through the development of biological substitutes. To achieve these goals, an artificial extra cellular matrix (ECM) and a source of cells are required. Although skin tissue constitutes a small amount of the body weight, skin damage such as burns and diabetic diseases can cause serious health complications. Tissue engineered replacements play an extremely important role in the treatment of chronic skin wounds. Skin tissue replacement techniques should be easy to perform for applying to the wound location. Skin tissue replacements must be readily adherent with good physical and mechanical properties, and be non-antigenic. The ultimate goal is to design and develop skin tissue engineering techniques that lead to novel and biomaterials-based skin replacement therapies¹⁵. The magnetic nanoparticles have been widely utilized for the tissue engineering applications to diagnose the damaged cells and to heal the wounds.

4.4. Potential anticancer agents

Using magnetic nanostructures as drug delivery carriers is an active research subject on the intracellular application of magnetic nanomaterials. The conventional and straightforward strategy for drug delivery using magnetic nanoparticles is the use of polymer to encapsulate magnetic nanoparticles and the drugs together to form nanocapsules or nanomicelles, which may require complicated processes and result in modest efficiency. One could develop the magnetic nanoparticles that target a specific tissue or cell type for delivering the therapeutic agents to tumors and detecting and monitoring the transformation of the tumor by noninvasive magnetic resonance imaging. Moreover, the investigation of such multifunctional nanostructures may lead to the development of other types of multifunctional magnetic nanomaterials as novel therapeutics. It is likely that the initial verifications of these novel magnetic nanomaterials will arouse the research interests and drive their further development for *in vivo* applications.

4.5. Hyperthermia

To localize magnetic nanoparticles inside cells would also benefit another potential new therapeutic procedure – hyperthermia therapy. The possibility of treating cancers by artificially induced the increase of temperature has led to the development of many different devices designed to heat malignant cells while spare surrounding healthy tissue. When the magnetic nanoparticles are exposed to AC magnetic fields, due to their high specific absorption rate, the particles become powerful heat sources and destroy the targeted tumor cells. Whereas the majority of hyperthermia therapy devices are restricted in their utility because of unacceptable coincidental heating of healthy tissue, magnetic hyperthermia therapy is appealing because it offers a way to ensure that the calefaction only happens in the intended target tissues. Although there are different arguments on the contribution of extracellular and intracellular hyperthermia, the magnetic nanoparticles as closer to the targeted cells will show better hyperthermia effect. For the tumor treatment using magnetic hyperthermia, great efforts have led to the pre-clinical trials. However, there are still challenges on guiding the magnetic nanoparticles inside the tumor cells for cancer therapy. Hence there are many question which have to be answered before the applications of hyper-

thermia therapy : for example, how to design stable magnetic nanoparticles that can to circulate in the blood compartment for a long time and to surface graft ligands on the nanoparticles to facilitate their specific internalization in tumor cells.

4.6. Intracellular manipulation

The successful demonstration of intracellular manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles will be useful in the biological applications. This strategy may offer a useful tool to investigate the difference between the apical and basolateral domains in polarized cells by the asymmetric localization of magnetic nanoparticles that carry specific ligands, to provide an effective way for specifically manipulating the functions of proteins in a desired intracellular location, and ultimately to introduce a new approach for understanding basic cellular processes and functions. However, the lack of truly monodispersed fluorescent magnetic nanoparticles still will be an issue for their biological applications. It is also observed the nanoparticles aggregated a little before intracellular manipulation. So the manipulation and tracking of single-nanoparticle inside the cell would be superior but remains a challenge because of the complex environment inside the cell, the inhomogeneity of the nanoparticles, and the high cost of the experimental setup.

4.7. Water/Wastewater treatment

Heavy metal contamination of aqueous environment is an increasing worldwide problem. Heavy metal is well known to cause serious environmental and health problems due to their bioaccumulation through the food chain, and causes serious damage to the nervous and endocrine systems of human beings. Therefore, the development of selective and efficient methodologies for detecting and removing heavy metals from aqueous media is in great demand. During recent few years, the majority of scientific research and large scale field applications of materials for treatment of wastewater containing heavy metals has focused on magnetic nanoparticles, activated carbon, carbon nanotubes, biosorbents, zero-valent iron, and photocatalysts. Among all these materials, magnetic nanoparticles, possessing the capability to treat wastewater at industrial scale and being convenient for mag-

netic separation, are most promising materials for heavy metal removal.

Magnetic nanoparticles such as magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) have been investigated to resolve various environmental problems, such as removing toxic metal ions and radioactive elements, capturing of microbial pathogens and organic dyes, accelerating the coagulation of sewage, and remediation of contaminated soils¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The magnetic nanoparticles possess high surface area, high chemical stability and optimal magnetic properties, which lead to high adsorption efficiency, highly efficient removal of contaminants, and easy and rapid separation of adsorbent from solution via external magnetic field.

Magnetism of the nanomaterials is a unique property that autonomously assists in water/wastewater purification by influencing the physical properties of contaminants in aqueous solutions. Thus, magnetic separations of pollutants have been used extensively in wastewater treatment and environmental cleanup. Magnetic iron oxide nanomaterials are promising candidate for larger scale wastewater treatment due to their easy functionalization, low cost, high adsorption capacity, strong physicochemical stability, and easy separations. Thus, these nanomaterials can be efficiently utilized for the treatment of wastewater containing hazardous dyes and toxic metal ions. In the following sections, we have described the application of magnetic nanoparticles for rapid removal of heavy metals from aqueous environments.

Recently, Feng *et al.*¹⁹ synthesized monodisperse carboxyl functionalized superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4(\text{np})\text{-COOH}$. Representative TEM images of the $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4(\text{np})\text{-COOH}$ nanoparticles deposited from a water dispersion and dried under ambient conditions revealed the presence of clearly defined features of an average size of $\sim 8\text{-}17$ nm with narrow sized distribution. They examined their ability to adsorption of Cd^{2+} from aqueous solutions. The adsorption efficiency of the particles for Cd^{2+} was on the order of $0.17\text{-}0.20$ $\mu\text{mol Cd/mg Fe}_3\text{O}_4(\text{np})\text{-COOH}$, which was among the highest reported in the literature. As reported by the authors, the adsorption efficiency of the 8 nm particles was a bit higher than that for the 17 nm analogues. It had been clearly observed that an increase in the acidity of the media led to desorption of Cd^{2+} .

In order to provide long term high quality water or to enable water recycling, Girginova *et al.*¹⁰ recently synthesized silica coated magnetite particles for magnetic removal of Hg^{2+} from water. Silica coated magnetite particles derivatized with dithiocarbamate groups were evaluated as magnetic nanodrivers to remove trace levels of Hg^{2+} from aqueous solutions using a simple external NdFeB magnet. The authors reported that the uptake efficiency for Hg^{2+} was significantly higher for the particles bearing dithiocarbamate groups at the surface (74%), as compared to the non-derivatized silica coated magnetite (24%). On the basis of this study, one can suggest that this efficiency of nanomaterials is related to the high stability of the chelates formed between the dithiocarbamate group and Hg^{2+} .

Recently, Gautam *et al.*²⁰ synthesized the Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles via a coprecipitation route for the adsorption of Ni^{II} ions from aqueous solutions. The TEM images showed that the synthesized nanomaterials were spherical in shape and the material was highly crystalline in nature. Most of the prepared nanoparticles were in the size range of $\sim 7\text{--}15$ nm. The pH of zero point charge (pH_{pzc}) of Fe_3O_4 was 6.2. Magnetic measurements of magnetite nanoparticles were investigated with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) at room temperature in the applied magnetic field sweeping from -50 to $+50$ kOe. The magnetic saturation value of the magnetite was 84 emu/g. Such an excellent magnetic property means that as-prepared magnetic nanomaterials have strong magnetic responsivity and be separated easily from the aqueous solution with the help of an external magnetic force. The Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles was used for the removal of Ni^{II} from aqueous solutions. The removal of Ni^{II} is strongly dependent on pH of the medium with enhanced adsorption as the pH turns from acidic to alkaline side. The process was very fast initially and the maximum adsorption was observed within 35 min of contact time. The kinetics of the removal, tested with pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second-order and intra-particles diffusion model, showed better agreement with pseudo-second-order rate kinetics ($k_2 = 6.740 \times 10^{-7}$ to 8.023×10^{-9} $\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$). The adsorption data was modeled with Langmuir, Freundlich, Dubinin-Radushkevich, and Temkin isotherms and yielded good fit with Freundlich isotherm model. The nanoscale Fe_3O_4 particles have considerable Langmuir adsorption ca-

capacity to Ni^{II} removal in the range of 209.205 to 362.318 mg g⁻¹. The adsorption process was endothermic with positive value of ΔH (101.209 kJ mol⁻¹) and spontaneous in nature (ΔG : -13.338 to -17.266 kJ mol⁻¹). The results have established good potentiality of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles to remove Ni^{II} from aqueous solutions.

5. Health and environmental impact of nanotechnology

The use of engineered nanoparticles in the environment as a consequence of the development of nanotechnology is a serious case of concern of environmental biologists worldwide. However, a few studies have already demonstrated the toxic effects of nanoparticles on various organisms, including mammals. Nanotechnology is still in discovery phase in which novel materials are first synthesized in small scale in order to identify new properties and further applications²¹.

Perception and knowledge are important parts of public understanding of nanotechnology. They can be influential for achievable benefit obtained and the possible risks and hazards. Therefore, detail understanding of their sources, release, interaction with environment, and possible risk assessment would provide a basis for safer use of engineered nanoparticles with minimal or no hazardous impact on environment. Thus, ecotoxicology of nanoparticles will be closely related to their intrinsic properties as shown in Table 1. Increase surface activity, mobility, and diffusion and adsorption ability are some other effects.

A further comprehension of the structure-function relationships in nanomaterials matter could lead to new protocols for nanomaterials manufacture wherein high precision, low waste methods are included. Some criteria could be taken into account referring to nanoparticles release and effects study on nature including human beings :

- Nanoparticles effects should be scale dependent and not the same in larger scale or agglomerates. This means that effects may be quite different to adopt specific and more appropriate regulations.
- These differences are based on size, surface chemistry and other specific interactions depending on the scale. Thus, the same mate-

rial may have different regulations through the different sizes presented.

- Effects must be conclusive to those products which commercialization is imminent. So, the nanoparticles presented in the final product may be the ones, which the studies should focus on.
- For the novelty of some materials, data to extrapolate environmental effects are difficult to obtain; so enhanced simulation system are needed.

The wide application of engineered nanoparticles and their entry into the environment, the study of their impact on the ecosystem and a growing concern in society regarding the possible adverse effects of manufactured nanoparticles has been raised in recent years. Therefore, it is required to study their release, uptake, and mode of toxicity in the organisms. Furthermore, to understand the long-term effect of nanoparticles on the ecosystem, substantial information is required regarding their persistence and bioaccumulation.

Table 1. Biological effects due to physicochemical properties related to ecotoxicology of nanomaterials

Physicochemical properties	Toxicological findings	Biological effects
Size	Affects reactivity and permeability of cells and organs	Increase biodistribution of nanoparticles in environmental system
Surface/volume ratio	Higher reactivity	Inflammatory effects
Chemical composition	Increase in UVA absorption, higher activation of reactive oxygen species in cell media	Cancerigen, cell proliferation reduced
Aggregation state	More pronounced cytotoxic effects	Cytotoxicity
Surface charge	Charged nanoparticles present higher deposition degree in tissues	Bioaccumulation in brain, lungs and others

6. Challenges in areas

- Environment, health and safety : clarifying the risks which may arise from the use of nanotechnology in the water industry and from

the presence in water of nanoparticles released into the environment from industry or agriculture.

- Technology transfer challenges, in bringing nanotechnology from research to industrial use, in transferring the technology to the point of use and in making the appropriate choice of technology to meet local circumstances.
- Communication : knowledge sharing and capacity development between the communities of researchers, engineers, management and administrators and end users.
- System : the need for new or adapted business models to facilitate the integration of new technologies into the water industry and increase appropriate adoption of technology.
- Intellectual property rights in water-related nanotechnology and ensuring a sound strategy for intellectual property protection and use in the context of this emerging technology.
- Adoption challenges, which may include, in both developed and developing countries, cost, availability of supply, technical and local management, safe disposal and reluctance to adopt new technologies.
- Economic feasibility of using nanotechnology and other technologies to address the global water challenges and the impact of investments in water-related nano-infrastructures within the region of implementation.

7. Proposed actions to address these challenges

- Strengthening science, engineering and commercial linkages : Support activities in water and nanotechnology which have the potential to enhance communication, understanding and collaboration between stakeholders, drawing on the experiences of national good practice in the use of other technologies for the enhancement of water systems.
- Fostering international linkages : Identify good practice in managing international co-operation to address the issues of access to and management of water, and support the national development of and/

or engagement in such cooperations for water and nanotechnology.

- Developing supportive platforms : Increase coherence and co-ordination in supporting the development of nanotechnology for water research and development, including water resource management. Pricing water will not only improve its management, but will also strengthen incentives for innovation related to water.
- Fostering informed and balanced approaches : Determine, at national level, the best ways to support and engage in work on the risks and benefits of nanotechnology in providing clean water at both national and international levels.
- Developing strategic roadmaps : Consider at national and international levels the best financial means for water provision and good resource management and implement them in parallel with technology-based solutions.

8. Future perspectives

The prospect of replacing damaged tissue with regenerated tissue would impact and change medical science definitely and radically. Today's interest in applying nanotechnology to regenerative medicine is growing owing to its capacity for producing nanostructures that are able to mimic natural tissues as well as nanoparticles for use in delivery systems.

The strategy relies on the development of intelligent materials that would be able to send signals to the stem cells already present in the diseased or damaged tissue niches that would then trigger the regeneration process²². Nanotechnology is a powerful tool for creating these 'smart' materials. This approach is challenging and is still far from being achieved. Among other advantages, it would raise the possibility to have such cell-free materials ready 'off the shelf' and to be able to use them as and when required. However, the magnetic nanoparticles have been successfully applied for the treatment of metal ions and dyes containing water and wastewater. Finally, because nanotechnology is a novel tool, the concern about the safety of nanomaterials used in regenerative medicine for human health has not been addressed in a sufficient and satisfactory manner. Before nanomaterials will be used in human applications, it will be necessary to carry out consistent and comprehensive studies to ensure their innocuousness.

9. Concluding note

Nanotechnology played an important role in the biological field such as in treatment and cure of cancer, diagnosis of damaged cells, drug delivery and for remediation of environmental pollutants from water and wastewater. Many of the magnetic nanoparticles have proved their ability to treat cancer cells and have been successfully applied for to remediate heavy metals and organic dyes from wastewater of industrial effluents. Bare nanomaterials have high surface area to volume ratio but get easily oxidized in the acidic environmental conditions. Hence, many of the nanomaterials have been synthesized and functionalized with organic or inorganic moieties to enhance the functional groups on the surface and to stabilize the nanomaterials in the extreme environmental conditions. Further it has been noticed that the functionalization of nanomaterials by the organic or inorganic molecules may decrease the surface area in comparison with their bare nanoparticles.

Notes and References

1. H. Goesmann and C. Feldmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 1362.
2. J. H. Jung, J. H. Lee and S. Shinkai, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 4464.
3. R. D. Ambashta and M. Sillanpaa, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2010, **180**, 38.
4. A. H. Lu, E. L. Salabas and F. Schuth, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, **46**, 1222.
5. Y. F. Shen, J. Tang, Z. H. Nie, Y. D. Wang, Y. Ren and L. Zuo, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2009, **100**, 4139.
6. K. P. Singh, S. Gupta, A. K. Singh and S. Sinha, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2011, **186**, 1462.
7. L. Sun, C. Tian, L. Wang, J. Zou, G. Mu and H. Fu, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2011, **21**, 7232.
8. H. Wang, N. Yan, Y. Li, X. Zhou, J. Chen, B. Yu, M. Gong and Q. Chen, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2012, **22**, 9230.
9. F. M. Koehler, M. Rossier, M. Waelle, E. K. Athanassiou, L. K. Limbach, R. N. Grass, D. Gunther and W. J. Stark, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, **5**, 4862.
10. P. I. Girginova, A. L. Daniel-da-Silva, C. B. Lopes, P. Figueira, M. Otero, V. S. Amaral, E. Pereira and T. Trindade, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2010, **345**, 234.

11. P. L. Lee, Y. C. Sun and Y. C. Ling, *J. Anal. Atom. Spect.*, 2009, **24**, 320.
12. S. Laurent, D. Forge, M. Port, A. Roch, C. Robic, L. V. Elst and R. N. Muller, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 2064.
13. A. Akbarzadeh, M. Samiei and S. Davaran, *Nano. Res. Lett.*, 2012, **7**, 144.
14. J. Gao and B. Xu, *Nano Today*, 2009, **4**, 37.
15. A. Mohamed and M. Xing, *Int. J. Burn Trauma*, 2012, **2**, 29.
16. S. J. Lee, J. H. Cho, C. Lee, J. Cho, Y. R. Kim and J. K. Park, *Nanotechnology*, 2011, **22**, 375603.
17. Z. Yong-Gang, S. Hao-Yu, P. Sheng-Dong and H. Mei-Qin, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2010, **182**, 295.
18. H. Yong-Mei, C. Man and H. Zhong-Bo, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2010, **184**, 392.
19. Z. Feng, S. Zhu, D. R. Martins de Godoi, A. C. S. Samia and D. Scherson, *Anal. Chem.*, 2012, **84**, 3764.
20. R. K. Gautam, P. K. Gautam, S. Banerjee, S. Soni, S. K. Singh and M. C. Chattopadhyaya, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2015, **204**, 60.
21. M. R. Wiesner, G. V. Lowry, P. Alvarez, D. Dionysiou and P. Biswas, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **15**, 4337.
22. E. Engel, A. Michiardi, M. Navarro, D. Lacroix and J. A. Planell, *Trends Biotechnol.*, 2007, **26**, 39.